

Notes on Partition of n into k Parts – $P(n,k)$

Introduction

For $P(n,k)$ equal to the partitions of n into k parts, in probability related investigations, it could be useful to know how many non-zero parts of $P(n,k)$ have m as maximum value. In this work we will derive such formulas, both for $P(n,k)$ and for $P(n)$ and $Q(n)$, where $Q(n)$ is the partition without repetition. We also present a formula for calculation of $P(n, k)$.

Nomenclature notation: The meaning of the notation $P(n, k) = m$ (partition of n into k parts) is the following: there are m different ways to write n as a summation of exactly k non-zero terms. The order of terms doesn't matter. Each way is called "part" of the partition $P(n, k)$.

To begin with, we will discuss a useful reduction formula for $P(n,k)$, that simplify its computation.

$P(n,k)$ reduction

The evaluation of $P(n,k)$ can be simplified if $t=2k-n > 0$. In this case:

$$P(n,k) = P(n-t,k-t) \quad (1)$$

For instance:

$$P(250,235) = 176 \rightarrow t = 235*2-250 = 220 > 0 \rightarrow P(250-220,235-220) = P(30,15) = 176$$

Equation (1) is a consequence of:

$$P(n,k) = \sum_{i=1}^k P(n-k, i) \quad (2)$$

and (2) has been obtained by iteration of the well-known recurrence $P(n,k) = P(n-1,k-1)+P(n-k,k)$

It is also important to note that:

$$P(n,k) = \sum_{i=1}^k P(n-k, i) = \sum_{i=1}^{n-k} P(n-k, i) \quad (3)$$

as all the terms with $i > n-k$ are zero.

Using (2), we get:

$$P(2n,n) = \sum_{i=1}^n P(n, i)$$

Note that $P(2n,n) = P(n)^1$

An example of such reduction is the following:

$$P(13,8) \equiv P(10,5) = P(5) = 7$$

Visually, we have $P(13, 8)$ [Table A]:

6	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
5	2	1	1	1	1	1	1
4	3	1	1	1	1	1	1
4	2	2	1	1	1	1	1
3	3	2	1	1	1	1	1
3	2	2	2	1	1	1	1
2	2	2	2	2	1	1	1

Using (1) and the fact that $t = 3 > 0$, this becomes $P(10,5) = 7$

Visually, $P(10,5)$ is [Table B]:

6	1	1	1	1
5	2	1	1	1
4	3	1	1	1
4	2	2	1	1
3	3	2	1	1
3	2	2	2	1
2	2	2	2	2

This, and any other, example shows that “reduction” corresponds to eliminating “1” t -times, while leaving unchanged everything with value different from 1. Visually, this corresponds to eliminating all columns containing only 1s.

For simplicity sake, it’s always convenient to reduce $P(n,k)$, if possible, as working on smaller numbers is usually easier.

Search for the number of parts of $P(n,k)$ with maximum value m

Each part of $P(n,k)$ (visually, a row of the partition table) has a maximum value m . Such a value can have multiplicity larger than 1 and it is, usually, written at the beginning of the part spanning from $\left\lceil \frac{n}{k} \right\rceil$ (n/k rounded up) to $n-k+1$.

The number of parts with maximum value m is indicated as $P(n,k)_m$

For instance:

¹ Math.stackexchange.com/questions/3405205

$P(16,7)$ (irreducible) has $m_{\min} = \left\lceil \frac{16}{7} \right\rceil = [2.28] = 3$, $m_{\max} = 16-7+1 = 10$ and $P(16,7)_5 = 6$ as shown in the attached Table C.

In generality, the number of parts starting with m is given by:

$$P(n,k)_m = P(n-m, k-1) - \sum_{i=m+1}^{n-k-m+2} P(n-m, k-1)_i \quad (4)$$

The average of m is defined as: $m_{\text{ave}} = \left\lfloor \frac{m_{\max} + m_{\min}}{2} \right\rfloor$.

Continuing the example above, $m_{\text{ave}} = \left\lfloor \frac{10+3}{2} \right\rfloor = [6.5] = 6$.

For $m \geq m_{\text{ave}}$, (4) becomes:

$$P(n,k)_m = P(n-m, k-1) \quad (5)$$

In the example above, we get $P(16,7)_7 = P(16-7, 7-1) = P(9,6) = 3$. Visually, in Table C, this is like using only the three parts starting with "7" and the partition to the right of the first column containing "7", i.e. $P(9,6)$.

Graphically, we will represent $P(9,6)$ as "4.1.1.1.1.1 – 3.2.1.1.1.1 – 2.2.2.1.1.1".

Using (1) and $t=3$, we get $P(9,6) = P(6,3) = P(3) = "4.1.1 – 3.2.1 – 2.2.2"$.

For $m < m_{\text{ave}}$, the sum in (4) is an iterative procedure. Visually, we compute the value of the part of $P(n,k)$ to the right of the first column, that only contains m . Such portion of the partition is equal to $P(n-m, k-1)$ without the terms with m larger than $m_{\text{ave}} + 1$ and smaller than $n-k+2$ ($m_{\text{ave}} + 1 < m < n-k+2$), where m_{ave} and m are calculated on $P(n-m, k-1)$.

To compute such parts, the procedure is the same as for the base partition through iteration for $m < m_{\text{ave}}$. Note that m_{ave} diminishes at each iteration as the portion of the partition becomes smaller each time.

For instance:

$P(16,7)_4 = 7$ because terms with $m = 5, 6, 7$ could be removed from $P(12,6) = 11$ (where $P(12,6)$ is $P(n-m, k-1)$) i.e. :

$$P(16,7)_4 = P(12,6) - P(12,6)_5 - P(12,6)_6 - P(12,6)_7.$$

Moreover, (4) implies that:

- $P(12,6)_5 = P(7,5) = 2$
- $P(12,6)_6 = P(6,5) = 1$
- $P(12,6)_7 = P(5,5) = 1$

So that $P(16,7)_4 = 11 - 2 - 1 - 1 = 7$ (same result as in Table C).

It's possible to use (4) iteratively, as, for instance, in computing $P(16,7)_3$. In this case we get:

$$P(16,7)_3 = P(13,6) - \sum_{i=4}^8 P(13,6)_i$$

Also, $P(13,6)$ has $3 < m < 8$ and $m_{ave} = 5$. This means that to be evaluated, the $i=4$ term in the summation requires using (4) once again, as $i=4$ is smaller than m_{ave} . In this case we get:

$$P(13,6)_4 = P(9,5) - \sum_{i=5}^5 P(9, 5)_5$$

which becomes $P(9,5) - P(9,5)_5 = P(9,5) - P(4,4) = 5-1 = 4$.

As $P(9,5)_5$ yields $m_{ave} = 3 < 5$, no more iterations are required.

All other terms in the summation have $m \geq m_{ave}$, so that:

- $P(13,6)_5 = P(8,5) \equiv P(6,3) = 3$
- $P(13,6)_6 = P(7,5) \equiv P(6,4) = 2$
- $P(13,6)_7 = P(6,5) \equiv P(2,1) = 1$
- $P(13,6)_8 = P(5,5) \equiv P(1,1) = 1$

Which leads to $P(16,7)_3 = 14 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 - 1 = 3$.

This example is shown in Table C, with all details for $P(16, 7) = 28$.

Case with null terms

Let $PZ(n,k)$ be the partition of n in k parts, among which null elements are allowed.

For instance, $PZ(6,3) = 7$ [Table D]

6	0	0
5	1	0
4	2	0
3	3	0
4	1	1
3	2	1
2	2	2

It is straightforward that:

$$PZ(n,k) = \sum_{i=1}^k P(n, i) \tag{6}$$

For instance, as it can be seen using Table D, $PZ(6,3) = P(6,1) + P(6,2) + P(6,3) = 1+3+3 = 7$

From (6), it follows that:

$$PZ(n,k)_m = \sum_{i=1}^k P(n, i)_m \tag{7}$$

Allowed m values range from $\left\lfloor \frac{n}{k} \right\rfloor$ (as for $P(n,k)$) to n (maximum value).

Ex: $PZ(16,4)_8 = 10$

$$PZ(16,4)_8 = P(16,1)_8 + P(16,2)_8 + P(16,3)_8 + P(16,4)_8 = 0 + 1 + 4 + 5 = 10.$$

It's important to point out that the well-known, base recurrence

$$P(n,k) = P(n-1,k-1) + P(n-k,k) \tag{8}$$

doesn't generally hold for PZ(n,k) because, in this case, terms for $k > n$ are not zero. For instance, $PZ(3, 5) = 3$ i.e. $(3 / 2.1 / 1.1.1)$.

Equation (8) holds for PZ only if $n-k \geq k$ in the second term of the recurrence.

Number of parts of partition P(n) with maximum value m

Let $P(n)_m$ be the number of parts of partition P(n) with maximum value m . The values of m range from 1 to n , and $m_{ave} = \left\lfloor \frac{n+1}{2} \right\rfloor$. In this case, (4) becomes:

$$P(n)_m = P(n-m) - \sum_{i=m+1}^{n-m} P(n-m)_i \tag{9}$$

For instance:

$$- P(8)_3 = P(5) - \sum_{i=4}^5 P(5)_i = P(5) - P(5)_4 - P(5)_5 = 7 - 1 - 1 = 5$$

From P(8), where P(8)=22, we have the following selection of the partition [Table E]:

3	3	2				
3	3	1	1			
3	2	2	1			
3	2	1	1	1		
3	1	1	1	1	1	

- The same result can be obtained using the known relation²:

$$P(n)_m = P(n,m) \tag{10}$$

$$\text{As we get } P(8)_3 = P(8, 3) = 5$$

Number of partitions without repetition Q(n) with maximum value m

Similarly, to the result for P(n), for all values of m we get:

$$Q(n)_m = Q(n-m) - \sum_{i=m}^{n-m} Q(n-m)_i \tag{11}$$

For instance, for $n=14$ and $m=6$:

$$Q(14)_6 = Q(8) - \sum_{i=6}^8 Q(8)_i = Q(8) - Q(8)_6 - Q(8)_7 - Q(8)_8 = Q(8) - Q(2) - Q(1) - Q(0) = 6 - 1 - 1 - 1 = 3$$

On the calculation of P(n,k)

²Da Wolfram MathWorld. Partition Function.

Simple ways to calculate $P(n,k)$ when $k > 4$ are not available. However, it is possible to calculate $P(n,k)$ using the formulae for calculation of $P(n)$.

(See, for example, Mathworld. Wolfram.com/PartitionFunctionalP.htm – formula 24.)

It is well known that, indicating as before with $P(n)_m$ the number of partitions of $P(n)$ with maximum value = m , we have

$$P(n)_m = P(n, m)$$

But, as seen in (9), we have the relation

$$P(n)_m = P(n - m) - \sum_{i=m+1}^{n-m} P(m - m)_i$$

Consequently

$$P(n, m) = P(n - m) - \sum_{i=m+1}^{n-m} P(n - m)_i \quad (12)$$

For instance, the value of $P(16, 7)$ – that from Table C we know is 28 –

$$P(16,7) = P(16 - 7) - \sum_{i=8}^9 P(16 - 7)_i = P(9) - P(9)_8 - P(9)_9$$

Using (12) we have

$$P(9)_8 = P(1) = 1 \quad P(9)_9 = P(0) = 1$$

and consequently

$$P(16,7) = P(9) - P(1) - P(0) = 30 - 1 - 1 = 28$$

Attachment – Table C

$$P(16, 7) = 28 \quad P(16,7)_5 = 6$$

$$m_{\min} = \left\lfloor \frac{16}{7} \right\rfloor = 3 \quad m_{\max} = 16 - 7 + 1 = 10 \quad m_{\text{ave}} = \left\lfloor \frac{10+3}{2} \right\rfloor = 6$$

10	1	1	1	1	1	1
9	2	1	1	1	1	1
8	3	1	1	1	1	1
8	2	2	1	1	1	1
7	4	1	1	1	1	1
7	3	2	1	1	1	1
7	2	2	2	1	1	1
6	5	1	1	1	1	1
6	4	2	1	1	1	1
6	3	3	1	1	1	1
6	3	2	2	1	1	1
6	2	2	2	2	1	1
5	5	2	1	1	1	1
5	4	3	1	1	1	1
5	4	2	2	1	1	1
5	3	3	2	1	1	1
5	3	2	2	2	1	1
5	2	2	2	2	2	1
4	4	4	1	1	1	1
4	4	3	2	1	1	1
4	4	2	2	2	1	1
4	3	3	3	1	1	1
4	3	3	2	2	1	1
4	3	2	2	2	2	1
4	2	2	2	2	2	2
3	3	3	3	2	1	1
3	3	3	2	2	2	1
3	3	2	2	2	2	2